

Classification of Psychosis Subtypes Using a Novel Wearable Platform and Machine Learning Methods

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ABSTRACT

Constituting a leading source of disability and suicidality, the conundrum of mental diseases has been growing to become one of the staggering challenges the world is facing today. Unfortunately, psychiatry has not kept pace with the evolution the other medical disciplines have seen recently, a problem primarily stemming from the traditional mental health diagnostic classification systems—the DSM and ICD. With low reliability, proven with biological research evidence, these symptoms-based diagnostic criteria have been adversely affecting the research and clinical psychiatry. The calls to redefine psychiatric nosology have been responded to with different efforts. For instance, the NIMH RDoC project was envisioned to be a step to organize the psychological research community around a DSM-free template, with a long-term goal of the application in clinical settings. However, the first ten years of this initiative did not witness the impact initially anticipated. While the alluring possibility of understanding mental illnesses has motivated some researchers to employ the emerging technology of machine learning in their investigations, the majority of these studies were designed based on the heterogeneous DSM diagnostic entities as the gold standard—which affected the reliability of their results. Contrarily, this proposed research follows a recent promising direction that employs the bottom-up approach starting from biological measures to re-stratify psychological disorders. Although the previous efforts in this avenue were primarily utilizing brain-based biomarkers, this study aims at demonstrating the feasibility of using the autonomic physiological measures to reclassify psychiatric conditions—specifically, psychosis. This hypothesis is based on the autonomic dysfunction of schizophrenic patients demonstrated by several authors, with some works indicating a continuous change in the physiological measures in correlation with the severity of the disease. A novel wearable platform will be developed in this investigation and used for collecting the data required to design and evaluate the machine learning models throughout the study.

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RESEARCH PLAN

A. Specific Aims

The key objective of the research here proposed is to demonstrate the feasibility of using machine learning techniques and wearable health devices in identifying the biological subtypes of psychosis based on the autonomic physiological measures. The long-term goal of this effort is to use these technologies on a large scale to redefine mental health nosology and enable the utilization of precision psychiatry in clinical settings. In order to realize these targets, three fundamental specific aims have been defined as follows:

Aim 1: Development of an integrated novel wearable health platform capable of monitoring multimodal autonomic physiological measures and a data logging software:

Aim 1A: Design and fabrication of the wearable system hardware in addition to the development and implementation of the firmware.

Aim 1B: Development and implementation of the data logging software.

Aim 1C: Evaluation of the developed wearable technology through comparison to gold-standard commercial devices.

Aim 2: Collection of the physiological data and assessment of the cognitive performance of patients with psychosis, followed by the extraction of potential biomarkers:

Aim 2A: Acquisition of the autonomic physiological measures using the developed wearable platform and conduction of neurocognitive assessment on patients with psychotic features.

Aim 2B: Apply signal processing techniques on the collected physiological data in Aim 2A to extract associated features that have the potential to be biomarkers for the biological subtypes of psychosis.

Aim 3: Development of machine learning models to cluster the patients with psychosis to biological subgroups

Aim 3A: Development of a clustering model to generate the biological subtypes_of patients with psychosis based on the features extracted in Aim 2B.

Aim 3B: Conducting the different statistical analyses to study the differences among the diagnostic groups and resulting psychosis subtypes on the basic demographic and clinical data, in addition to the physiological measures from Aim 2B.

B. Background and Significance

Mental disorders are one of the staggering challenges the world is facing today. They not only lower the quality of life [1] and academic achievement [1-3] levels of the affected individuals, but they are also considered as a leading cause of disability [4-6] and suicidality [7-9] worldwide. While patients associated with other medical disciplines are diagnosed through procedures like medical imaging and blood tests, psychiatry heavily relies on the interviews and self-reports of the patients to "fit" them into diagnostic categories based on the observed clinical symptoms [10]. Traditionally, the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM) and the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (ICD) have been utilized to establish the delineation of these classifications. For instance, Table 1 shows the criteria defined in DSM 5 to diagnose schizophrenia patients—one of the most debilitating mental health diseases. This subjective method of evaluation has been deemed questionable due to its lack of

biological basis [9, 11, 12] and poor clinical outcomes—in terms of high rates of false positives [13] and comorbidity [14] and, consequently, low efficacy of the pharmaceutical and the psychotherapeutic treatments [15-17]. Therefore, it is no surprise that research studies that use the DSM- and ICD-based nosological entities as a gold standard in studying the etiology of the psychological diseases reveal a high degree of biological underpinnings overlap between these entities [18-28] and, nevertheless, heterogeneity within the distinct classifications [29-33]. This subpar performance in the clinical settings and the revealed orthogonality between the outcomes emerging from psychopathology research and the current symptomatology-based psychological diagnoses speak to the imperative demand for a tectonic change in the psychiatry intellectual basis towards a precise and biologically-validatable demarcation of the mental disorders.

Table 1: Diagnosing schizophrenia based on DSM 5 [34].

Criterion A. Two (or more) of the following (At least one of these should include 1-3):

1. Delusions
2. Hallucinations
3. Disorganized speech
4. Grossly disorganized or catatonic behavior
5. Negative symptoms (i.e., diminished emotional expression or avolition)

Criterion B. One or more major areas functioning, such as work, interp, are markedly below the level achieved prior to the onset.

Criterion C. Continuous signs of the disturbance persist for at least 6 months.

Criterion D. Schizoaffective disorder and depressive and bipolar disorder with psychotic features have been ruled out.

Criterion E. Substance / general medical condition exclusion.

Criterion F. If there is a history of autism spectrum disorder or other communication disorder of childhood onset, the additional diagnosis of schizophrenia is made only if prominent delusions or hallucinations are also present for at least 1 month (or less if successfully treated).

The issue of intra-heterogeneity and inter-similarity in mental diseases has been present since the inception of psychiatric categories. For instance, Bleuler, in his 1911 book [35] that defined schizophrenia for the first time, referred to it as “Gruppe der Schizophrenien,” which was later

translated to English as “Group of Schizophrenias.” However, even in the most recent version of the DSM, schizophrenia is still described as a single disease. Efforts have been made over the past century to address the heterogeneity of mental diseases. Early studies attempted to identify subtypes of diseases based on clustering of symptoms, such as the work of Farmer et al. in 1982, which focused on identifying symptom-based subtypes of schizophrenia [36]. However, this approach has been criticized for being subjective, and the generated subtypes are temporally unstable, with evidence showing that patient subtypes can change within 5 years [37].

Expectedly, the National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH) was aware of the current psychiatric diagnostic systems' limitations, and that was part of the reason behind the birth of a new vision aiming at solving these problems in 2009 [38]. It did not start with a target of replacing the current diagnostic systems (i.e., DSM and ICD); instead, the NIMH hypothesized that this shift would need to organize the research efforts first. This vision led to the start of the Research Domain Criteria (RDoC) project as an initiative to create a new framework for the psychopathology research community. A template called the RDoC matrix has been created for researchers to follow the NIMH proposed framework and is being updated regularly [39]. The RDoC matrix rows correspond to fundamental behavioral components (defined by the NIMH and are called constructs) that are grouped into six domains, and the columns identify the units of analysis—measurement units or dimensions to study the different constructs. The research that adopts the RDoC scheme may choose one or more constructs—rows of the RDoC matrix—as the independent variables and any of the analysis units—the RDoC matrix columns—as the dependent variables. It is the investigators' responsibility to identify the group of patients for their studies that might cross or include distinct DSM/ICD entities [38].

Despite being weighed as an essential step towards the transformation demanded for mental health, the RDoC initiative is not anticipated to have any forthcoming impact on clinical psychiatry. As the NIMH stated while starting the project: "NIMH views RDoC as the beginning of a transformative effort that needs to succeed over the next decade... and may ultimately fail to deliver the transformation we seek in clinical care" [38]. Moreover, unfortunately, the NIMH project did not have the anticipated influence on the psychological research community, and only a few empirical studies adopted the RDoC scheme [40, 41]. A potential reason for this failure in attracting research efforts is the framework constructs. The way that the RDoC template was defined added a layer of complexity in identifying the relevant constructs to the psychopathological studies [42]—for example, Ford *et al.* [43] work was dedicated to demonstrating how to study hallucinations based on the RDoC scheme. Additionally, the maturity of these constructs has been a matter of debate [44], and the fact that the framework has been receiving revisions over the years puts the efforts that follow the RDoC scheme at the risk of being obsolete if the constructs they study change in a future revision [41].

Recently, Machine Learning (ML)—as the leading artificial intelligence modality—has garnered a position of significance in both the commercial and the research arenas. Typical applications of ML include speech-recognition, spam e-mails detection [45], video games [46], and pattern recognition-based medical diagnostic systems—e.g., detection of skin cancer from medical skin images [47] and Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) from Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) brain scans [48]. Simply put, ML can be described as a set of computational algorithms that automatically "learn" the specifics of the solution from data instead of being defined by the designer [49]; these algorithms can be grouped broadly into two categories: supervised- and unsupervised-ML models [50]. In supervised-learning algorithms, ML models are designed to

predict specific outputs based on the input data. In contrast, the unsupervised-learning models are used to discover clusters/patterns of data with no prior knowledge about the outputs. Figure 1 illustrates the differences between the supervised- and unsupervised-ML models with an example of using MRI scans for medical diagnosis (supervised-learning) or finding subtypes of diseases (unsupervised-learning). It is worth noting that features used in ML models for medical applications are often referred to as biomarkers if they can be considered a signature of the disease. Thus, in Figure 1, if a brain region's size is different in a specific disease than in healthy individuals, it is considered a disease's biomarker. The NIH Biomarkers Definitions Working Group defined a biomarker as "a characteristic that is objectively measured and evaluated as an indicator of normal biologic processes, pathogenic processes, or pharmacologic responses to a therapeutic intervention" [51].

Figure 1: Illustration of the supervised- and unsupervised-ML concepts and steps.

Following the majority of the medical disciplines, psychiatry has witnessed an exponential increase in utilizing ML techniques over the past few years [52]—see Table 2 for sample efforts. Nevertheless, mental health research's dominant agenda has been employing the DSM/ICD diagnostic entities as the studies' gold standard. As these diagnoses are repeatedly found incongruent with the biological research evidence [9], the robustness of the ML models that utilize them has been called into question [53, 54]. While some authors have proposed the sample size used in the psychiatric studies as the reason behind the low and inconsistent performance of the psychological ML models [55], Neuhaus and Popescu [56] provided evidence to refute this claim. In that effort, the authors compiled ML-based studies of schizophrenia (total number of samples $N = 5563$), major depressive disorder ($N = 2042$), and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (N

= 8084) to investigate the relationship between the sample size and the ML model accuracy. Contradicting the expected behavior of the ML models performance, the accuracy of the psychiatric models was negatively correlated with the sample size—i.e., the accuracy decreases with the increase of the sample size—indicating a problem in the structure of the samples resulting from the heterogeneity of the DSM/ICD categories.

Table 2: Example studies of using ML in psychiatry

Data Source	Example Studies
EHR	Prediction of suicide ideation [57] and depression [58].
Social media	Prediction of suicide ideation [59] and depression [60]. Detection/classification of mental health-related posts [61].
Neuroimaging	Detection of schizophrenia [62] and MDD [63] using fMRI.
EEG/ERP	Classification of unipolar and bipolar MDD [64] from EEG. Prediction of schizophrenia from ERPs [65].
Genetic data	Prediction of BD from the whole-exome sequencing data [66].
Audio/Visual Data	Prediction of psychosis from speech [67]. Prediction of depression from facial expression from video recordings [68].

EHR: Electronic Health Record, MDD: Major Depressive Disorder, fMRI: functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging, EEG: Electroencephalography, and ERP: Event-Related Potentials.

Latterly, an auspicious trend in psychiatric research has emerged as a result of the synergistic integration between the mental health ML-based efforts and the concept of the NIMH project. These studies were able to circumvent the RDoC constructs and DSM/ICD diagnoses by adopting the bottom-up approach in re-segregating the mental health diseases as follows: (i) choosing a study sample based on the investigation hypotheses which may span different DSM/ICD entities, (ii) extract the distinguishing signatures from the participants' data, (iii) apply the ML techniques to cluster the subjects into different groups based on these biomarkers, and, (iv) validate these groups using data measures that have not been used in the clustering process. This concept was first applied to identify the subtypes of psychosis. Psychosis can fundamentally be defined as the dissociation from reality, essentially characterized by the symptoms of delusions and

hallucinations [69], and may include disorganized thinking and behavior, in addition to catatonia [70]. Although psychosis is not defined as a diagnosis in the DSC/ICD, it has been referred to as a set of manifestations that patients with different diagnoses may experience. The effort done by Lewandowski *et al.* [71] was one of the first studies to demonstrate the bottom-up methodology in distinguishing the subgroups of the psychotic participants. The authors recruited a sample of subjects diagnosed with schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder, and psychotic bipolar disorder DSM-based diagnoses. The features used in this work were based on nine neurocognitive assessment scores. Then, an ML model using the k-means clustering algorithm was used to classify participants based on their neurocognitive biomarkers. The model generated four groups that cross the original diagnoses of the patients. The four subtypes were then validated by employing different clinical assessment scores. Another leading work that pursued this avenue is the investigation done by Clementz *et al.* [72]. This study was conducted on individuals with the same diagnoses in Lewandowski *et al.* effort. However, the ML model's biomarkers were extracted from the patients' EEG data in addition to a neurocognitive assessment score. Three psychosis subtypes that are also orthogonal to the subjects' DSM classifications were observed in this investigation employing the K-means algorithm. The authors called these groups biotypes as biological data was utilized in the clustering process. The validation of the three biotypes was achieved by means of the MRI scans and the scores of Birchwood social functioning scale.

Identifying the relevant type of biomarkers is a critical component for the studies implementing the bottom-up approach in rebuilding the mental health diagnoses. Broadly speaking, six kinds of measures can be utilized as fundamental data sources for the ML model features—as shown in Figure 2. Although neurocognitive assessments have been used to classify psychosis in a previous study [71], it is expected that biological data will be more reliable and objective than the cognitive

performance test batteries that depend on the subjects' accuracy in answering the questions. Thus, only the biological features were considered in this investigation. It is worth noting that establishing new reliable psychiatric nosology requires a large amount of data (and, hence, a large number of subjects), enough to cover all the variations of the conditions and validate the ML models before the clinical utilization. Choosing genes, molecules, cells, or neural circuits as the source for the biological data required for clustering the psychological categories will be highly challenging due to their complexity and high data dimensionality, not to mention the feasibility of the data collection process. Thus, in this research, it is hypothesized that the optimal data source would be at the physiological measures level for different reasons. First, physiological signals are easy to process and cluster. Second, recent advancements in biosensing and the internet of things (IoT) industry facilitate collecting different physiological data modalities non-invasively on a large scale through portable/wearable means. Finally, the biological validity of the biotypes resulting from the physiological biomarkers clustering will serve the efforts targeting the lower biological underpinnings in two ways. One, these subtypes can replace the DSM categories and the RDoC constructs as the independent variables for these investigations. Two, the homogeneity among each resulting biotype data will allow for conducting studies on a smaller scale, increasing their feasibility.

Figure 2: The different levels of the biological measures

Most of the efforts to identify physiological biomarkers in psychiatric research have been centered around the brain either using neuroimaging (e.g., fMRI) or EEG—resting or ERPs (49, 50, 52, 70, 71). Although many studies were able to extract different features from these modalities that can help understand the etiology of the mental disorders, the current technology of these measures prevents them from being widely adopted in large-scale studies and, consequently, redefine the mental health diagnoses in many ways. As previously mentioned, a large amount of data is needed to redefine the mental health categories, which will be very expensive using MRI and EEG. Secondly, the biomarkers' reliability depends on the quality of the collected data, which can be challenging, especially with EEG. Finally, collecting ecologically valid data is imperative to detect the changes in measures associated with daily life events that cannot be achieved using the brain-based biomarkers—even EEG, as it is highly prone to artifacts and noise and needs to be conducted in a highly controlled environment at least in the current time until a reliable, portable EEG system can be utilized in similar studies. Therefore, it is of paramount importance to identify new

biomarkers based on affordable technologies that can be used in large-cohort studies with a high degree of ecological validity.

Schizophrenia, a major mental disorder mainly characterized by psychotic symptoms, has been linked to developing cardiovascular diseases (CVD) in different investigations—e.g., [73], which has been hypothesized to be a significant reason for the high rate of mortality associated with this disease [74, 75]. This observation urged the research community to study and assess the cardiac functions and, then, the whole autonomic nervous system (ANS) in schizophrenic patients revealing an ANS impairment among the affected individuals. HRV was reported to be reduced in patients with schizophrenia by many studies—e.g., [76, 77]. While some efforts—like, [78, 79]—suggested that the usage of medications causes these changes in the HRV, Mujica-Parodi et al. [80] compared medicated and unmedicated subjects with schizophrenia and observed a lower HRV in both groups. In addition to the HRV, the QT interval of drug-naive schizophrenic patients' ECG has been indicated to be longer and with a higher degree of variability [81, 82]. These physiological changes do not only follow a yes/no format—i.e., existing/non-existing—yet they have also been shown to take continuous values. For example, a number of authors have recognized that the severity of the psychotic symptoms is negatively correlated with the HRV [83-86]. Also, some other studies suggested that the Electrodermal Activity (EDA) of participants with schizophrenia is positively correlated with the strength of the disease [87, 88].

Moreover, in their recent work, Schulz et al. reported a higher respiration rate and altered cardiorespiratory coupling not only in individuals with schizophrenia but in their healthy first-degree relatives as well. Interestingly, other researchers have also provided evidence for autonomic dysfunction in the first-degree symptoms-free relatives of schizophrenic subjects—for instance, [83, 89]. This suggests a potential role of genes in these alterations and refutes the claims that

propose the medications or even stress and anxiety as the reasons behind these variations. Similarly, mounting other contributions have investigated the different domains of the autonomic physiological measures in schizophrenia patients and their relatives, mostly summarized by Bar (89) in Figure 3. In aggregate, a reduced vagal tone has been notified in participants with schizophrenia and, to a lesser degree, in their first-degree healthy relatives. These reports allow the conclusion that autonomic physiological measures-based biomarkers can be utilized in identifying the biological subtypes of psychosis, which has been adopted in this proposed investigation.

	Heart rate	Breathing rate	Blood pressure	Heart heart variability	Peak heart rate	Blood pressure variability	Baro-reflex sensitivity	Pupil-diameter	Tachy-gastria
Patients with schizophrenia	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↔	↓	↑	↑
Healthy first degree relatives	↑	↔	↔	↓	↔	↔	↓	n.d.	↑

Figure 3: Summary of the efforts investigating the autonomic dysfunction in schizophrenia patients and their healthy first-degree relatives—adapted from [90].

Wearable health monitoring technologies have seen an increase in sales revenue worldwide from \$16B to \$26B between 2016 and 2018 and will reach, anticipatedly, \$73B by 2022 [91]. This provides a clear indication of the potential impact that exists for the wearable device market. Today, most commercially available technologies are geared more toward the novelty market with applications directed at general activity and health monitoring. Such technology, however, has the potential to develop into more sophisticated health diagnostic platforms considering advances within core integrated circuit systems, wireless networks, cloud computing, and machine learning-based decision support systems. Considerable interest has been garnered in individualized medicine, occupational monitoring associated with high-risk jobs, and cognitive and health

assessment for military personnel. Unfortunately, regarding existing marketed lifestyle wearables, when it comes to monitoring health-related vital signs such as heart rate and other measures, the data is often overly processed to avoid sporadic readings. To use such technologies towards medical and health-related real-time analyses, especially those that feed into decision support systems, such approaches are seldomly viable due to the low confidence in the reported metrics. Thus, a new wearable health platform will be developed in this effort to monitor the various autonomic physiological measures that will be essential for this study.

C. Research Design and Methods

The fundamental hypotheses for this investigation are:

Hypothesis 1: DSM/ICD diagnoses with psychotic features can be combined into a single sample and reclassified based on their biomarkers into new biologically valid groups.

1.1: Previous work:

Different studies have demonstrated the ability to define the subtypes of psychosis based on a sample that combines patients with schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder, and bipolar disorder with psychosis [71, 72].

1.2: New in this investigation:

Previous investigations—e.g., [92]—showed different degrees of overlap in the biological underpinnings between the different DSM diagnoses with psychosis. Therefore, it is hypothesized that, for more accurate demarcation of the psychotic subtypes, all categories of patients with psychotic features need to be involved in this study.

Hypothesis 2: Biomarkers based on the different autonomic physiological measures can be used to define the biological subtypes of psychosis.

2.1: Previous work:

- Previous research used neurocognitive scores and/or EEG/ERP-based biomarkers only to redefine psychosis subcategories [71, 72].
- Other efforts studied the changes of the autonomic measures in patients with psychosis. However, they did not target identifying the psychosis groups based on the observed biomarkers, and the majority of the studies included patients with schizophrenia only [81, 90, 93].

2.2: New in this investigation:

The different autonomic physiological measures will be used to define the subtypes of psychosis using wearable technology.

The following methodology will be taken in this work to prove these hypotheses.

Aim 1: Development of an integrated novel wearable health platform capable of monitoring multimodal autonomic physiological measures and a data logging software:

Due to the nature of this study, the development of a new and more robust wearable health system is needed to monitor the required autonomic physiological measures on patients for the following reasons:

1. Although the commercial market has a wide range of wearable devices available, most products target general activity monitoring, providing either heavily-averaged derived

measures (e.g., HR, motion, and oxygen saturation) or overly processed signals (e.g., ECG).

2. The majority of the commercial off-the-shelf wearable monitoring devices target only a few (or single) physiological metrics and lack the integrity of the various measures required for this investigation.

Approach:

Aim 1A: *Design and fabrication of the wearable system hardware in addition to the development and implementation of the firmware.*

The functionality of the system to be developed in this investigation will be divided among two separate wearable devices of different form factors; a wristband and a smart-shirt. The wristband will have a photoplethysmography (PPG) sensing setup utilizing three light-emitting diodes (LEDs) of the green, red, and near-infrared (NIR) wavelengths in addition to a wide-range photodiode (PD)—see Figure 4a. An application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC) will be used for the PPG signals modulation and data acquisition. Besides, the wrist-worn device will incorporate a far-infrared (FIR) non-contact skin temperature sensor (Figure 4a) and electrodermal activity (EDA) recording interface. Two metal dry-electrodes will be utilized for the EDA, as shown in Figure 4b. The smart-shirt consists of a pluggable device (via snaps, see Figures 4c and 4d) to a custom shirt. This device will contain the board with the bio-signals interfacing and communication circuits in addition to the battery. The shirt will integrate a set of twelve dry-electrodes made of conductive silicone (J-Flex, UK) connected to the snaps using conductive thread—Figure 4e demonstrates this concept. Ten of these electrodes are for the cardiac activity monitoring via a 12-lead ECG acquisition system and distributed on the shirt according to the modified Mason-Likar 12-lead placement [94]. The other two electrodes are

for respiration tracking that will be implemented by measuring the change of the thoracic bioimpedance (BioZ) during the inhalation and exhalation processes. Both devices will have a 9-axis activity sensor (3-axis accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer) with a motion co-processor. The activity data will compensate for the motion artifacts in the bio-signals during the signal processing phase (Aim 2B). Table 3 summarizes the list of measures that will be implemented in each device, along with the potential ASICs that will be used in the prototypes.

Table 3: *The different measures implemented in the wristband and the smart-shirt wearable devices to be developed in this investigation and the potential ASICs to implement these measures.*

Signal Type	Specifics	Potential ASIC
Smart-shirt		
ECG	Eight channels for 12-lead ECG	ADS1298 (Texas Instruments, Dallas, Tx)
Respiration	Using thoracic bioimpedance	MAX30002 (Maxim Integrated, San Jose, CA)
Activity	9-axis motion	BNO085 (Hillcrest Labs, Rockville, MD)
Wristband		
PPG	Red/IR/Green wavelengths	MAX86141 (Maxim Integrated, San Jose, CA)
EDA	Metal electrodes on the dorsal wrist	MAX30002 (Maxim Integrated, San Jose, CA)
Skin Temperature	Contactless FIR-based	MLX90632 (Melexis, Ypres, Belgium)
Activity	9-axis motion	BNO085 (Hillcrest Labs, Rockville, MD)

Figure 4: The concepts of the wearable platform to be developed in this effort.

a) The bottom side of the wrist-worn device incorporates the PPG sensing setup and the skin temperature sensor. **b)** The top side of the wrist-worn device. The EDA metal electrodes can be seen in a and b. **c, d)** Demonstrate the smart-shirt concept and how the device snaps to the custom shirt. **e)** A conductive Silicon electrode connected to a snap via conductive thread.

For processing and Bluetooth communication, the nRF52840 chip (Nordic Semiconductor, Trondheim, Norway) will be used in both wearables. This chip incorporates a 32-bit Cortex M4F processor at 64MHz in addition to an integrated Bluetooth 5 low energy (BLE) communication interface. Specifically, the ISP1807 (Insight SiP, Sophia-Antipolis, France) module that integrates an nRF52840 chip along with the wireless communication antenna and the passive interfacing components is selected in this effort for its miniaturized size and good

antenna performance. The wristband will utilize the integrated BLE to transfer the raw signals wirelessly to the data acquisition application. However, an additional Wi-Fi module (BCM43362, Cypress Semiconductor, San Jose, CA) will be employed in the smart-shirt as the BLE bandwidth is not sufficient to transfer the raw data of the 12-lead ECG and the respiration monitoring. Although Wi-Fi communication will be used to transfer the bio-signals from the smart-shirt wirelessly, BLE will still be utilized for the initial communication setup (e.g., IP/Port exchange between the device and the data collection software). The printed circuit boards (PCBs) of the devices will be designed using EAGLE (Autodesk, Inc., San Rafael, CA) and fabricated at an external manufacturing facility (Beta LAYOUT GmbH, Germany); yet, the assembly of the boards will be done in-house.

The firmware will be developed in the C/C++ programming language. The SEGGER embedded studio (SEGGER Microcontroller Systems, LLC, Gardner, MA) with the GNU (GCC) compiler will be utilized. Nordic software development kit (SDK) will be used to handle the wireless Bluetooth 5 connectivity. The firmware will be broken up into three modules; the main module is responsible for the system initialization and overall power management, the hardware abstraction layer (HAL) module includes all the platform-dependent code, and the driver module manages the different onboard ASICs. Data packets will be used for signal streaming; each signal value will be packaged with a header indicating its type before being wirelessly transmitted. Different prototypes of the two wearables hardware and/or firmware may be developed during this investigation to enhance the functionality as the project progresses.

Aim 1B: *Development and implementation of the data logging software.*

Custom data acquisition software will be developed in this effort. Essentially, the application will serve as a client for the wearable system (both the wristband and the smart-shirt at the same time) to receive and log the data over the BLE/Wi-Fi connections with real-time signal plotting. The C# programming language using Microsoft Visual Studio will be used to build the program based on the Universal Windows Platform (UWP) technology and Windows 10 SDK. The software will have two main integrated modules for wireless connection and data logging. The connection module manages the BLE scanning and connection for the two wearables in addition to establishing the Wi-Fi communication for the smart-shirt. The data logging module handles the streaming packets received from both devices simultaneously. All the received raw signals will be logged locally and displayed in real-time using the Syncfusion UWP framework (Syncfusion Inc., Morrisville, NC).

Aim 1C: *Evaluation of the developed wearable technology through comparison to gold standard commercial devices.*

Human testing will be performed with a protocol that involves a simultaneous collection of the same bio-signals using the wearable technology to be developed in this investigation and a set of commercial off-the-shelf devices. Ten healthy student subjects will be recruited from the University of Toledo (UT) College of Engineering for this process, and the data will be collected at the Biomedical Optics and Sensing Laboratory (BMOL) at the UT. Next, a comparison between the physiological data collected using the custom wearables and the gold standard devices will be conducted for assessment. The feedback from this evaluation may lead to building modified prototypes of the hardware. Before starting any testing with human participants, a study protocol will be submitted as part of the application to the UT Institutional

Review Board (IRB) that includes all the activities involving human subjects in this investigation. Upon approval, the human study activities in this effort will be assured to comply with all the IRB requirements.

Aim 2: Collection of the physiological data and assessment of neurocognitive performance on patients with psychosis, followed by the extraction of potential biomarkers:

The physiological data of interest will need to be collected during this investigation as the available datasets from previous efforts do not satisfy the requirements for this study due to at least one of the following reasons:

1. These datasets do not have all the required physiological measures collected on the same participants.
2. The subjects recruited to collect the data fall under a single DSM diagnosis only, which contradicts this study's fundamental objective.

Approach:

Aim 2A: *Acquisition of the physiological measures using the developed wearable technology and conduction of neurocognitive assessment of patients with psychotic features.*

The wearable platform proposed in this effort will be used to acquire the following physiological measures from the patient subjects: ECG, respiratory monitor, PPG, Skin temperature, and EDA, in addition to the activity data. All the raw signals will be transmitted wirelessly to the custom data acquisition software developed in this investigation. The elimination of wires in this setup will reduce the chance of using the study equipment in any participants' self-harm actions during the data collection sessions. This section of the data collection session will be 25 minutes long; the participants will be sitting on a chair with no

physical activities involved. An Oculus Quest (Facebook Technologies, LLC, Menlo Park, Ca) Virtual Reality (VR) will be utilized to relax the subjects (e.g., using natural scenes/sounds) in order to collect baseline measures or expose them to different stimuli—e.g., social stressor with a crowd scene or auditory stimuli using white noise. For neurocognitive evaluation, the Brief Assessment of Cognition in Schizophrenia score (BACS) (90) will be utilized. The BACS is a 35-minute battery that evaluates four cognitive domains: processing speed, reasoning and problem solving, verbal memory, and working memory. This score will not be used as an input to the clustering algorithm, yet as an external validator to the resultant groups, as will be explained in Aim 3B.

The data collection sessions will be one hour long and conducted in the facilities of the participants' treatment providers. Subjects will be recruited from the following mental health institutions: ProMedica Flower hospital, Northwest Ohio Psychiatric hospital, Mercy Health-Behavioral Health Center St. Charles hospital, Harbor center, and Zepf center. These hospitals and community mental health centers have been contacted and approved to participate in the study.

To estimate the sample size needed for the study, a power analysis has been performed using G*Power 3 [95]. The effect size of the changes in the autonomic physiological measures between the patients (primarily schizophrenia and bipolar disorder) and the control groups has been demonstrated to range from medium to large (Cohen's d value of ≥ 0.25) in the previous works—e.g., (75, 91, 92). Thus, a medium effect size (Cohen's d value of $= 0.25$) is utilized in this calculation. For the other parameters, the α and power ($1-\beta$) have been set to 0.05 and 0.8, respectively. As the statistical analyses will be performed primarily on the resultant biotypes from this investigation, the number of groups has been approximated based on the

anticipated subtypes of psychosis to be produced from the clustering process—which is expected to be four based on the previously discussed efforts [71, 72]—in addition to a control group. Different estimations have been conducted based on the analyses planned to be performed during the study—more in aim 3B. Table 4 summarizes the different results based on the specific statistical tests, which concludes that it is required to recruit at least 255 participants to detect a medium effect size using a significance level of 0.05 and a power of 0.8. It is worth noting that the post-hoc t-test will not be used in this work; however, it has been employed to approximate the sample needed for the post-hoc Tukey honestly significant difference (HSD) and Dunnett tests.

Table 4: Different sample size estimations based on the potential statistical tests to be conducted in the proposed work

Statistical Test	Effect Size	α	Power	Factors (Levels)	# of Covariates	# of Groups	Response Variables	Sample Size
Gender as Factor								
Two-way MANOVA*	0.0625	0.05	0.8	Groups (5) Gender (2)	NA	5	20	177
Two-way ANCOVA*	0.25	0.05	0.8	Groups (5) Gender (2)	3	5	NA	197
Post-hoc T-test**	0.5	0.05	0.8	NA	NA	NA	NA	255 (51x5)
Gender as Covariate								
One-way MANOVA*	0.0625	0.05	0.8	Groups (5)	NA	5	20	120
One-way ANCOVA*	0.25	0.05	0.8	Groups (5)	4	5	NA	196
Post-hoc T-test**	0.5	0.05	0.8	NA	NA	NA	NA	255 (51x5)

*MANOVA is the multivariate analysis of variance, and ANCOVA is the analysis of covariance.

**Performed as a two independent means test with a single tail (as the changes in the physiological measures are anticipated to be in one direction based on the previous efforts).

Unfortunately, to conduct this full expansive study, additional funding support would be required which is being pursued. However, this dissertation research is primarily proposed to demonstrate and to obtain the support of the main hypotheses in order to pave the way for a

large-cohort follow-up project. Thus, only a smaller feasibility study will be pursued as part of this research proposal, and this may be expanded if additional funding is received. It is anticipated that the sample size utilized in this study will be roughly 15-20% of the large cohort mentioned. A nine-month time slot will be allotted for the data collection, and patient subjects to be recruited will be distributed among the five categories listed in Table 5. As mentioned earlier, the detailed study protocol will be submitted to the UT IRB—in addition to the health providers’ IRBs as required—and no activities involving human subjects will be started prior to approval.

Table 5: Categories of patients to be included in the proposed study human trials with the relevant ICD-10 codes

Category	ICD-10 Code	Description
SZ	F20.0	Paranoid schizophrenia
	F20.1	Disorganized schizophrenia
	F20.2	Catatonic schizophrenia
	F20.3	Undifferentiated schizophrenia
	F20.81	Schizophreniform disorder
	F20.89	Other schizophrenia
SzAff	F20.9	Schizophrenia, unspecified
	F25.0	Schizoaffective disorder, Bipolar type
	F25.1	Schizoaffective disorder, Depressive type
BPD	F25.9	Schizoaffective disorder, unspecified
	F31.2	Bipolar disorder, current episode manic severe with psychotic features
	F31.5	Bipolar disorder, current episode depressed, severe, with psychotic features
MDD	F31.64	Bipolar disorder, current episode mixed, severe, with psychotic features
	F32.3	Major depressive disorder, single episode, with psychotic features
Others	F33.3	Major depressive disorder, recurrent episode, with psychotic features
	F21	Schizotypal personality disorder
	F22	Delusional disorder
	F23	Brief psychotic disorder
	F24	Shared psychotic disorder
	F28	Other psychotic disorder not due to a substance or known phys. condition
	F29	Unspecified psychosis not due to a substance or known phys. condition
F30.2	Manic episode, severe with psychotic symptoms	

SZ: schizophrenia, SzAff: schizoaffective disorder, BPD: bipolar disorder, and MDD: major depressive disorder.

Aim 2B: *Applying the signal processing techniques on the collected physiological data in Aim 2A to extract the features that have the potential to be biomarkers for the biological subtypes of psychosis.*

In order to utilize the unsupervised ML algorithms, signal processing methods have to be applied to extract the different features from the raw data collected in Aim 2A. These metrics will serve as inputs to the ML algorithm to cluster the psychotic patients into subgroups. To name a few, different HRV measures can be extracted from ECG and PPG signals—e.g., the standard deviation of the N-N intervals (SDNN), the root mean square of successive differences (RMSSD), the Respiratory Sinus Arrhythmia (RSA), and the power of the different frequency ranges of the N-N intervals data. Various measures may be obtained from the QRS complex, such as the ST and the corrected QT (QTc) intervals. Blood oxygenation can be estimated using the two-wavelength PPG sensor. From the raw EDA signal, Skin Conductance Level (SCL) and the Skin Conductance Response (SCR) measures may be extracted. The respiratory rate and the change of rate can be obtained through the thoracic BioZ signal. The activity data will primarily be used to compensate for the motion artifacts from the bio-signals in the preprocessing stage.

Aim 3: **Development of machine learning models to cluster patients with psychosis to biological subgroups.**

The autonomic physiological biomarkers from Aim 2B will be used to identify the subtypes of psychosis by employing unsupervised machine learning algorithms.

Approach:

Aim 3A: *Development of a clustering model to generate the biological subtypes_of patients with psychosis based on the features extracted in Aim 2B.*

In this effort, K-means will be mainly discussed for the sake of comparison with the previous efforts in this line of research; however, different clustering algorithms will be also implemented—e.g., DBSCAN, Hierarchical, and DEC. K-means is one of the widely used unsupervised machine learning algorithms in the literature to cluster unlabeled data into subgroups. Each of the resulting groups is described by a single point called the cluster centroid, the center (mean) of all the data points. In the beginning, the algorithm assigns K random centroids; then, the distances of all the observations to these centroids are calculated. Each point after this step is assigned to the group with the closest center, and the centroids' values are updated to the mean of the newly assigned data points. The last two steps are usually repeated until the algorithm convergence condition is met—which can be the minimum in-cluster variance, for instance. It is the user's responsibility to assign the number of clusters (K) and the distance formula to be used. Assigning the K value is one of the crucial steps in the K-means algorithm. A significant drawback of this method is that it returns K clusters even if there are no K groups in the data. Common methods of determining the optimum number of clusters are usually achieved by utilizing the gap statistics [96] or Silhouette score [97], which are primarily based on the distances of the data points to the other values in the same and the neighboring clusters in addition to the in-cluster data dispersion.

An artificial neural network (ANN) is a supervised ML technique consisting of an interconnected group of computationally simulated (artificial) neurons employing a mathematical model for information processing. As shown in Figure 5-a, essentially, an

artificial neuron's output is the summation of its weighted inputs. To allow for the emulation of complex systems, a function (called the activation function, e.g., tanh) can be applied to the result of this summation. In the training phase, a dataset with known outputs is used to optimize the network weights for the model to predict the unknown outputs of other datasets. An ANN model usually consists of numerous interconnected artificial neurons grouped into "layers," as shown in Figure 5-b.

Figure 5: a) the mathematical model of an ANN neuron and b) an example ANN model with four layers.

In this work being proposed, the K-means algorithm will be employed to group the patients based on the features obtained in Aim 2B to identify the biological subtypes of psychosis. The Euclidean metric will be used as the distance function. To pick the optimal number of clusters, a new innovative way will be utilized using the ANN in addition to the conventional metrics. In this method, for each value of K in the range of interest, a K-means algorithm will be utilized to cluster the patients. A portion of the patients' data with their corresponding clusters (from the previous step) will be used to build/train an ANN classifier. The rest of the dataset will be

employed to test the ANN model in predicting the correct subtype of the patients. An error metric (e.g., mean square error—MSE) will be calculated for each model, and the optimum number of clusters value will be determined based on the ANN with the minimum error. Figure 6 illustrates how K-means and ANN algorithms will be integrated into this effort. MATLAB (MathWorks, Natick, MA) will be used for ML development. In the case of the clustering process’s poor performance, the BACS score will be provided to the K-means as an additional input to the algorithm, and the same steps will be repeated to optimize the number of clusters.

Figure 6: The concept of using the K-means algorithm and ANN to identify psychosis subtypes

Top) How the K-means algorithm will be used to classify psychotic subjects into their biological subtypes. **Bottom)** ANN will be utilized to evaluate/optimize the biotypes by building models to predict the K-means algorithm output clusters. A K value that produces clusters with the best ANN predictability is considered the optimal number of clusters.

Aim 3B: *Conducting the different statistical analyses to study the differences among the diagnostic groups and resulting psychosis subtypes on the basic demographic and clinical data, in addition to the physiological measures from Aim 2B.*

Different statistical analyses will be performed throughout this study using the R statistical environment. Initially, the DSM diagnostic groups' variations will be compared using one-way ANOVA and Chi-squared tests on the demographic and clinical data. Tukey HSD and adjusted standardized residual analysis will be employed as the ANOVA and Chi-squared post-hoc tests, respectively, to locate the pair-wise differences between the cohorts. The clinical data will be extracted from the providers' EHR—see Figure 7 as an example from Harbor mental health center's EHD system. Upon the data collection and the extraction of the potential biomarkers, all the features will be standardized using Z-score to allow for equal weights in the clustering process. After generating the clusters—as described in Aim 2A—similar to the diagnostic groups, the psychosis subcategories will be compared based on the demographic and clinical data. Then, both the resulting biotypes and the original diagnoses will be studied as follows. First, a one-way ANCOVA test will be employed to study BACS scores with age and sex as covariates. Second, for each group of extracted features from the same physiological signal, a linear regression analysis will be conducted, and a one-way MANOVA test will be conducted for the measures that correlate between 0.3 and 0.9. Following the MANOVA tests, a one-way ANCOVA analysis will be conducted for each set of features that have statically significant results from the previous step. The potential covariates for this test are age and sex, in addition to medication and smoking data. All the ANCOVA tests in this stage will be followed by a post-hoc Dunnett's test to compare each biotype/diagnosis with the control group

as the psychosis subtypes will have been already generated to maximize their statistical differences.

Mental Status Exam

General
 Alert and Oriented x4 Yes No
 Grooming and Hygiene Good Fair Disheveled Poor
 Eye Contact Good Avoidant None
 Cooperative/Pleasant Yes No

Speech Regular rate, rhythm, and volume Specify

Psychomotor No problems seen Specify

Mood Euthymic Labile Dysphoric Elevated Anxious Irritable Expansive

Affect Broad Flat Blunted Constricted Guarded

Thought processes Logical Illogical Circumstantial Tangential Flight of Ideas Preoccupied
 Auditory Hallucinations Delusions Visual Hallucinations Paranoia Grandiose
 Referential Poverty of thought Loose associations

Suicidal None Reported Specify Ideation Intent Plan

Homicidal None Reported Specify Ideation Intent Plan

Memory and Recall Intact Specify

Intelligence Average Above Borderline Below

Insight and judgment Good Fair Poor

Additional Comments

Figure 7: A screenshot of the mental evaluation form adopted from Harbor mental health center's EHR

D. Project timeline:

Month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
Aim 1	1A																	
	1B																	
			1C															
Aim 2				2A														
													2B					
Aim 3																3A		
																3B		

E. Conclusion:

This investigation is primarily a proof of concept or feasibility study that may support and lead to the mentioned larger-cohort project. Proving the proposed hypotheses can impact psychiatry in both the research and clinical domains—summarized in Figure 8. The successful utilization of autonomic physiological data based on wearable technology to classify psychosis is anticipated to encourage larger psychological studies with high ecological validity. This will impact the empirical research community by increasing their studies' feasibility, pushing the race of improving the current psychiatric nosology in the clinical settings. Moreover, basic research efforts will potentially reach levels of understanding the etiology of mental health diseases that were not attainable due to the traditional diagnoses' heterogeneity.

Additionally, a wearable device capable of detecting the distinct biomarkers associated with mental illnesses is anticipated to directly affect clinical psychiatry in three main ways. One, prognosis, enabling early intervention for high-risk individuals. Two, quantitative diagnostics—in the form of a range rather than a binary classification. Three, enhancing treatment output, especially for outpatients, through continuous monitoring. With these anticipated impacts, a new chapter may begin where psychiatry is able to follow the other medical disciplines in applying precision medicine to enhance the treatment of patients based on biological evidence rather than subjective interviews.

Figure 8: The potential impact of proving the proposed fundamental premise in the short-, medium-, and long-term.

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